

BLENDED LEARNING – NEED OF HIGHER EDUCATION**Dr. Ravindra Mirajkar***Associate Professor, Mahavir Mahavidyalaya, Kolhapur 7/E, Vaishali Parisar,
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Blended learning or the integration face to face and online instruction (Graham 2013) is widely adopted across higher education with some scholars referring to it as the 'new traditional model'. Blended learning forces us to consider the characteristics of digital technology, in general and information communication technologies more specifically. Blended learning can enhance students learning outcomes, improve student's motivation and it is effective way for achieving learning objectives. Blended learning also spends lower cost for training and it may enhance the students learning experience.

Keywords: *Blended learning, Need and advantages of Blended learning*

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Introduction

As the world goes digital, the e-learning sector too has evolved to embrace online tools to make learning more engaging, relevant, contextual and immersive. The rapidly changing landscape. Simply means that education and training practices should incorporate the best of both of the worlds. The virtues of traditional classroom settings and the advantages of the online world. Today's world is highly driven by technology. All organization in various sectors, business, education, health care, banking and others are influenced by rapid pace of technological development and innovation. The education sector where student centric learning is the core aspect to take into consideration, is highly influenced by technology. In teacher education institutions, a variety of learning approaches have been incorporated for the betterment of learning which ultimately makes the teaching effectively. One of the new innovative technology is used in teacher education is web based technology. The web based technology explores the knowledge and lays immense effect on the teaching learning environment. Both the teacher educator and teacher trainees will be benefited by those technologies. It makes the teaching learning process favorable and easier.

Literature review:

Study of blende learning process in Education context (September, 2012) International journal of modern education and computer science. Betil Yilmaza conducted an extensive survey to find students' academic achievement by introducing blended learning technique in the 'Instructional technologies and material development course. The result showed that, blended learning environment has positive effect on academic achievements level and their frequency of participation to forum affected their views about blende learning environment face to face interaction in blended learning application had the highest score. The result demonstrated the importance of interaction and communication for the success of online learning.

Objectives:

1. To understand the concept of blended learning
2. To comprehend the need of blended learning in teacher education
3. To understand the advantages and disadvantages of blended learning.
4. To aware the role of teacher in blended learning.

Scope:

This paper is focused on only the concept of blended learning and the role of teacher in this process.

Research Methodology:

This study is based on library resources. Literature survey is done for this presentation of blended learning.

What is blended learning?

Blended learning is one of the aspect of web base technology. Blended learning is blending of different techniques or resources and applying them in an interactively meaningful learning environment. Learner (Teacher trainees) should have easy access to different learning resources in order to apply the knowledge and skills. They learn inside and outside of the classroom. This approach will combine face to face instruction with computer mediated instructions. It also applies IT activities with the assistance of innovative educational technologies using computer, tablets, mobiles, sky tv channels and other electronic media. Blended learning is learning that is facilitated by the effective combination of different modes of delivery, models of teaching and styles of learning and it is based on transparent communication amongst all parties involved with a course (Heinz and Procter). Blended learning can combine the positive aspect of two learning environment, classroom based learning and e-learning (Monk and Graham).

Need of blended learning in teacher education

Teaching and learning process is most important part in teacher education. Learning requires some sort of experiences to takes place. Each learner is different from other in that we have to consider the following differences are as follows:

1. Interest span
2. Needs
3. Aptitude
4. Achievement
5. Variation of time needed to master a specific learning task
6. Abilities t deal with complexities
7. Degree to motivate creativity
8. Problem solving differences
9. Degree to which a learner need to guided

Blended learning provided individual learning experiences within learning environment by using mixture of media, strategies and method. These learning experiences promote interactions that allows learner recall information so that it may be remembered and combine it with other experiences. So, that new knowledge bases are formed.

Blended learning

- Peer-peer instruction
- Technological integrator
- Project base learning

- Virtual learning platforms
- Community based learning
- Global connections
- Essential skill development
- Teacher led instructor

Advantages of blended learning

A blended learning environment allows learner to 'See' concepts in real world settings in a virtual environment. The context and a practical implementation of the concepts increase student interest and make learning more interesting and innovative. This learning helps to independent and collaborative learning experience for the students. The use of information and communication technologies has been found to improve access to as well as student attitudes towards learning. By incorporating information technology into class projects, communication between lectures and part time students was improved and students were able to better evaluate their understanding of course material via the use of 'computer based qualitative and quantitative assessment modules' in a study by Alexander and Mokenzie (1998).

It is a formal education programme in which a student learns at least in part through online delivery of content and instruction with same element of student control over time, place, path or pace.

Disadvantages of blended learning

Blended learning has a strong dependence on the technical resources with which the blended experience is delivered these tools need to be reliable, easy to use and up to date in order for the use of internet to have a meaningful impact on the learning experience. IT learning can serve as a significant barrier for students attempting to get access to the course materials, making the availability of high quality technical support.

Role of teacher trainees as instructor

Teacher trainees can combine two or more methods of teaching in practice lesson. In case of blended learning they can combine technology based material and face to face session and present their content. Blended learning can also be applied to the combination of e-learning a learning management system using computers in a physical classroom, along with face to face interaction. An instructor (teacher trainees or teacher educator) can begin a course with well-structured introductory lesson in classroom and then proceed with follow up material online.

The role of the instructor is critical as this requires a transformation process to that of learning facilitator, assisting students with computer skills and application, helping them access the internet and encouraging them to be independent learners.

Conclusion

In this way, we find that how blended learning make their impact every aspect of teacher education. No doubt, traditional methods of teaching and learning cannot be avoided at any cost but blending of these traditional methods with e-learning strategies may be fruitful for teachers and learners to promote the efficiency and effectiveness of the teacher education.

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